

Establishing TVET Applied Research, Production and Extension centers in National Polytechnics can Spur Industrialization

Charles E. Butiko¹

¹The Eldoret National Polytechnic

*Corresponding author's Email: charlesbutiko@gmail.com

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Abstract

According to Applied Research, applied research aims at finding a solution for an immediate problem facing a society, or an industrial/business organization and is considered to be a non-systematic inquiry usually launched by a company, agency or an individual in order to address a specific problem. While organizations in Kenya aspire to industrialize, lack of clarity on the appropriate strategy to go about it can stand in their way. Kenya Vision 2030 proposes application of science, technology and innovation to up the productivity and efficiency levels across the economic, social and political pillars. It therefore underscores the crucial role played by research and development (R&D) in spurring economic development. A survey across TVET institutions in Kenya shows that important industrial skills are offered in training but with one missing link: a coordinated central linkage between the institutions and industrial players as a way of enhancing the utilization of the skills to enhance productivity for mutual benefit. A grounded theory and discourse analysis of the survey confirms attempts by the institutions and line directorates to make this a reality. By a case study with a peer higher education institution, this research concludes that establishing Applied Research, Production and Extension centers is the best way to go for mutual benefits between the TVET institutions, industrial players and the trainees in terms of quality of labor via the trainees; industrial products innovation and development and entrepreneurial industrialization. Important areas for industrialization can be tapped and developed in partnership with industrial players, external research partners, research & development and innovation sponsors, and relevant government agencies.

Key words: Applied Research; Production & Extension Centres

Introduction

While there has been profound dedication to linking technical training to industrialization in Kenya, there is still much to be done to ensure this type of training adds more value to the industrial workforce, inspires innovation, entrepreneurship, and solves community challenges within its scope. Upgrading applied research in technical institutions can contribute to early industrial incubation; industrial stakeholder-academia collaboration; inspire innovation; orient technical trainees to industrial work environment to help reverse supply-driven training to demand-driven; and inspire skill-based entrepreneurship. This means a direct relationship between applied research and related pilot production and dissemination and sharing of related services & information within and without the learning institutions and line industries. This strengthens the observation by Wanyeki, P. et al (n.d) who highlight the importance of technical skills in spurring industrialization (which is key to vision 2030) and the need to equip TVET institutions to enable them to provide the skills consistent with emerging technologies. This gives a strong argument for explicit establishment of ‘Applied Research, Production and Extension’ (ARPE) Centres in technical institutes to complement what is already existing in support of technical and vocational training.

While this sounds novel, there have been attempts towards this, albeit with some missing gaps which should be filled to realize the goal of ARPE Centres in TVET fully. A survey across some technical institutions reveals some of the initiatives. Approaches like encouraging applied research through innovation and skills competitions amongst trainees and trainers; industrial exposure through visits and attachment; some partnerships with industrial players; and classwork related research have been sporadic and so not sufficing to fully equip technical trainees to match emerging industrial needs. Some of the gaps as clearly seen in the approaches include but not limited to: stand-alone nature of the approaches; lack of clear policy and institutional framework guiding the full establishment of coordinating centers; lack of or poor funding; and lack of elaborate engagement platforms between collaborating players.

This paper brings out the findings of a survey across some of the institutions obtained via observation; contact interviews; texts and documents. It analyses the findings qualitatively and brings recommendations at both the umpire and implementing institutional levels. It proposes a policy paradigm shift by TVETA to help address some of the above challenges. A guided decision

should be made if the proposed ARPE centres can be centrally managed under a new directorate or a sub-directorate in ‘TVETA strategy planning & research’ directorate with the technical institutions playing host to the centres for mutual benefits or if the centres can be placed as new departments in the technical institutions. This is clearly informed from the functions of the TVETA directorate of strategy planning & research which include but not limited to: initiating and engaging in development projects and research; establishing linkages and collaborations for best practice in TVET; and enhancing public-private partnerships in TVET and industry (TVETA 2023). This can bring up a needed collaboration to realize the centres and this paper proposes a pilot 10 centres in national polytechnics.

The much needed collaboration amongst players will aid in resources mobilization to achieve the needed infrastructure; equipment; and material; and even human labor to jumpstart, coordinate and run the ARPE centres which require organized interdisciplinary and intersectoral approaches.

This exploratory, casual, and descriptive survey whose findings are analysed thematically, seeks to bring out the attempts made towards establishment of ARPEs, especially in parts; show the gap left in combining the parts to bring up fully fledged running centres; and how the centres will serve as catalysts to rapid industrialization in Kenya. It brings out with whom and with what we can come up with such centres that will in spire industrialization as per the Kenya vision 2030 (Wanyeki, P. et al (n.d) while improving the quality of technical and vocational training. In the course of the research work up to the recommendations, this author declares that he did it out of a professional urge to bring up the idea for the good of all the target institutions and that there was no conflict of interest that guided the research.

Methodology

An exploratory, descriptive and casual survey was conducted in at least 10 technical institutions seeking to gather qualitative information on pertinent issues relating to the extent to which applied research was being carried out; whether there was a collaboration between the institutions and the industry and/or the neighboring communities; whether the immediate institutional community was benefitting from the applied research activities through institutional infrastructural development; if there were existing any patents, pilot projects, and industrial ready innovations resulting from

the applied research activities; and if there was sufficient policy framework supporting such initiatives. Related observations were also made through visits, texts and documents. Information was gathered from focus group discussion.

The information gathered was analyzed through content analysis; narrative analysis; discourse analysis; grounded theory; gap analysis for missing links towards industrial development; and grouped into themes bring out thematic analysis. The findings and discussion were done under such themes as: state of affairs on whether technical institutions were practicing applied research for industrialization; missing links in the attempts in applied research towards industrialization; and a conclusion and recommendation was done based on the stage of affairs and the missing links after gap analysis. A case study was established based on the JKUAT Research Production and Extension Centre which coordinates a number of research programs that contributes towards industrialization and a proposal on how to juxtapose applied research to technical institutions was done in the findings and discussion.

Findings and discussion

Towards ARPE Centres in 10 National Polytechnics to inspire industrialization

There is a clear distinction between basic research and applied research. While, basic research does focus on the advancement of knowledge, applied research directs its efforts toward finding a solution to a specific problem (Indeed Editorial Team 2023). It therefore means that basic research is researcher motivated, and supply driven, while applied research is problem driven or demand guided. Applied research is a call to come up with a solution based on a challenge, which is appropriate amongst the technical institutions. The efforts made by technical institutions in being at the forefront of using applied research to come up with solutions to challenges facing the society cannot go unnoticed. Are technical institutions in Kenya putting in effort to come up with programs based on applied research to catalyze industrialization? Are they promoting pilot projects development? are they promoting industrial partnerships with industry players? Are they dissemination industrial solutions to immediate communities? Are their skills programs developed in line with industrial demands? This leads us to discuss the findings of the attempts in applied research by the technical institutions that can contribute to industrial growth.

Attempts in applied research? Gaps in the attempts?

The technical institutions surveyed have followed ministry of education guidelines and come up with practical skills training programs that have industrial potential at various levels. A survey on policy guide towards promoting innovations towards industrial growth revealed that the ministry of education in Kenya has given provisions and platforms for both trainers, tutors, teachers to guide students in coming up with innovations in science and technology. Such innovations are showcased in various fora such as: the national science and technology congresses for high schools; World skills Kenya competitions for technical institutes; and science and innovation competition for technical colleges. There are other platforms which inspire participation in innovations such as: Kenya national innovation agency (KENIA) which invites innovators across the board; national commission for science, technology and innovations (NACOSTI); and National research fund (NRF). While some of these innovation promoting platforms are specific for technical institutes, others are general or skewed towards higher education and research. What was missing was central coordination of such innovations to realize maximum industrial potential. Beyond the competitions, there is need to bring out the best out of those innovations by addressing limitations like lack of patent guides; lack of pilot and commercialization models where possible in the innovations.

Beyond innovation promotion platforms, individual technical institutions have made tremendous efforts in guiding their students to make use of applied research to solve specific challenges identifiable in the regions they exist. A perfect illustration of this once came up when The Kisii National Polytechnic guided Mr. James Nyakundi, one of their students to come up with a solution to curb huge post-harvest losses in bananas widely grown in the region. This effort was effected in collaboration with The Kenya Industrial Research & Development Institute (KIRDI) and Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) (Nyamweya, 2022). This a good example of how applied research was employed to solve a challenge through collaborative approach premised on acquired technical skills. Mr. Nyakundi was enabled to become an entrepreneur based on his skills and knowledge. The fact that he went ahead to work with other institutions means that applied research players need to play as a team and it means that problem solving a continuous learning

opportunity. The missing link here lack of a platform that can identify several challenges in the community, work with students and trainers in the institutions to come up with workable solutions, engage other stakeholders, and help the trainees become entrepreneurs based on the acquired skills.

If such a platform were able to come up with a pilot production on site it would offer an opportunity for scale up and for partnerships with bigger industrial players or interested investors seeking technical advisory.

The survey revealed that there was scanty of purposeful technical knowledge repository which can document innovations, pilot projects, guide other trainees without having to start from scratch.

Apart from guiding trainees to use applied research to solve challenges by coming up with industrial products with partners, some institutions are bringing new features in the built-in environment to solve their own challenges. A good example of this is at The Eldoret National Polytechnic where there is an installed biogas plant to help bring down the costs of cooking and heating fuel at the Hospitality Institute. Such a project can serve three purposes: help the immediate institution cut down on their costs of operation; be used as a training resource for students (for instance chemical engineering, entrepreneurship, environmental science, hospitality, civil engineering, inter alia); and be an empirical guide for scalability for other potential users if the institution can build capacity in consultancy in biogas and renewable energy. This exposes a case of the missing platform to think through and come up with other areas for inclusion in the own infrastructural development that is based on application of specialized skills and knowledge to solve own challenges and link them to training and solutions provision.

One observable feature of applied research is that it entails continuous learning and gains much from observing what others have been able to achieve use knowledge and skills. To gain such exposure, almost all technical institutions organize for industrial visits and industrial internships since the latter is a prerequisite for several courses. Through such exposure, trainees and trainers are in a position to link their skills and knowledge to certain identifiable challenges based on best practice as observed and done in the industry. While this is presumably an ongoing practice, this research established that there are limitations such as: limited resources; communication challenges in planning for such programs; broken coordination between line departments and industrial liaison; and limited opportunities in the target industries. A centre to coordinate and plan purposefully such activities with an elaborate knowledge on prioritization based on: what is already available in the institution that can substitute such visits; available resources; and already established memorandums of cooperation. With such a center, coming up with memorandums of cooperation with industries on internships and visits is easier than haphazard plans. Through such centres, the trainees can be given minimum targets for any visits made so that the visits are more meaningful in helping develop the institution based centres. For instance, a visit to East Africa Portland Cement by chemical engineering students can be more meaningful if, for instance, the students can be tasked with the responsibility of coming up with a potential alternative material, locally obtained, that can be used as a binder in cement production based on the properties of the conventional materials in cement production. With such a task, it is possible to develop at a pilot level, own ‘cement’, which will be promotion of innovation.

Armed with technical skills and knowledge, trainers and trainees and technical institutes as whole, can be a hub for solutions provision to societal challenges. However, this survey observed uncoordinated efforts have killed this potential. Such solutions can be offered as industrial consultancies; applied research proposals for specific areas on need to need basis. Government, Non-government, private organizations, and individual investors should look up to organized technical institutions as to where to go to places when in need of certain solutions. Despite the fact that there are individual trainers who are offering such solutions, an institution stands to reap more from this initiative if there is a corporate coordination approach to motivate more trainers and trainees to come on board and offer such solutions. For instance, The Bukura Agricultural College is the place to go for good breeding pedigree pigs through their ‘Bukura Farm’ and the institution

has maintained this brand. Apart from just offering training in animal husbandry, they are able to offer such a solution to the society based on acquired knowledge and skills to help out farmers in the region. The missing link is a centre that coordinates and offers a platform for such a solution it can help the institutions get additional income streams and promote the application of knowledge for problem solving. Such a centre can organize for capacity building amongst its trainers and trainees who can sharpen their problem-solving capacities and continuously improve.

It was established that department specific memorandum of understandings or cooperation with industrial players are trending issues in technical institutions. A perfect illustration of this is like The Eldoret National Polytechnic's partnership with Bajaj motorbike makers to set up the Bajaj workshop within the precincts of Mechanical Engineering department. This can aid the trainees get hands on experience and work in an industry simulated environment. It helps train practically oriented motor bike mechanics applying acquired skills to help assemble and repair the machines which aid in local transport. Because this an excellent example such industrial coordination, there is a missing link for lack of a 'proposal factory' centre that can do several of such and coordinate with other departments to entrench more practical based learning and early industrial orientation amongst the trainees. These collaborations can be upscaled and make the institutions as 'brand ambassadors' for the partners. That can help out when it comes to organizing for industry-based short trainings targeting the neighboring community. From grounded theory, a paint manufacturer can partner with a technical institution doubling as its regional 'brand ambassador' to trainees potential trainers from the region based on their paint products. A common coordinating centre can come up with department specific interests and reach out to several potential industrial partners.

Applied Research borrows hugely from basic research with the clear distinction that while the former is demand-driven, the latter is supply driven. It means that there is little danger in benchmarking with a higher education and research centre in the drive to establish ARPE centres in technical institutions since there is provision for scope clarification at policy guide stage. One bench-mark institution based centre in the survey was the Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and technology Research Production and Extension (RPE) Centre. The JKUAT organogram for RPE is clearly illustrated in Figure 1 below:

Note: Adapted from: RPE Division JKUAT .

It is worthwhile to acknowledge that national polytechnics in Kenya already have the research division. However, this survey exposes a missing elaborate structuring of the division to accommodate more functions that would be able to accommodate several elements of pilot production; practical learning; trainer –trainee engagement in applied research; community engagement; collaborative linkages; and innovations promotion. Such development can include but not limited to : identifying areas of strength and developing specialized applied research centres around the themes; rolling out income generating units based on pilot production emanating from the identified applied research ideas targeting certain challenges in the community; engaging the ARPE Centres in reaching out to the communities, county governments, NGOs, and corporates with their solutions; or seeking partnerships on acquisition of equipment, material or sharing opportunities; applied research funds mobilization through structured projects proposals based on the thematic areas and academic departmental inputs; incubation and nurturing innovations within and without by targeting trainees, trainers, potential trainees in high schools,

private entrepreneurs seeking partnerships on incubation and innovation development; and offering applied research and consultancy services in identified thematic areas.

From the observed attempts by technical institutions to employ applied research to promote productivity, extension and drive industrialization, it is clear that the gaps have been pointed out. Two underlying observations in the attempts are clearly seen as: (i) the attempts can be taken a step further in this noble goal; (ii) the attempts can be centrally guided within the technical institutions. This definitely builds a very strong case for ARPE centres to help drive industrialization. Meaning the centre is the main gap in this coordination. Such a centre can make technical training more practical; more engaging; more problem-solving; more productive; income generating; and more entrepreneurially- orienting while preparing the trainees for the industry.

All the above needs investment in: infrastructure for relevant workshops; laboratories; fields; production parks; material; and the extra needed human resources.

At policy level, the TVETA directorate of strategy research and planning can guide on whether the ARPE Centres can be incorporated by strengthening the existing research divisions in national polytechnics or by letting the institutions host the centres for mutual benefit. It can also guide on if the ARPE can be rolled out as a new directorate under TVETA. Beyond the policy adjustments, there should be a strategy on identifying other collaborators to help actualize '*establishing TVET ARPE Centres in national polytechnics to spur industrialization*'.

Apart from policy restructuring, establishing memorandums of cooperation with relevant government departments, and the target collaborating partners after the initiative, line industries, geared towards rolling out the centres can help jumpstart the idea. For instance industries like vehicle assemblers, process plants, and spare parts manufacturers can be approached for collaboration in mechanical engineering or a related thematic area identified. A thematic area like in 'renewable energy and climate change' can support innovations and applied research in biofuels, solar, wind, inter alia and can attract support from promoters of climate change mitigation and adaptation technologies. A thematic area like 'water, waste water and waste management' can attract support from promoters of pollution control. Just as a thematic area in 'chemical technology products can attract collaboration with chemical products manufacturers. There is currently an

increasing interest in leather and leather products processing. A thematic area in ‘leather products’ can attract collaboration right from target communities, county governments, and national departments promoting leather development. A thematic area in ‘affordable housing’ can attract support from government departments, and private sector players in construction and construction machinery and this can help boost the idea of ARPEs promoting industrialization. Through a thematic area in ‘mentoring upcoming innovators’, TVETs can also get involved in reaching out to neighboring high schools to tap their innovations for incubation through ARPE Centres and help ‘create their future trainees’.

Conclusion and recommendation

Though there have been discrete applied research related activities in technical institutes in general and national polytechnics in particular, the need for purposely coordinating the activities and adding more players can catalyze industrialization in multi-fold: help churn out new innovations and products that can be incubated right at the institutions; help bring out industry-oriented trainees who would later work in the various sectors; help bring out skilled techpreneurs who would bring innovative contributions in industrialization; entrench the approach of collaboration between academia-industry for bigger impact of mutual benefits; help the society get solutions to their challenges through applied research; and enable the institutions play a mentorship role to upcoming innovators. While basic research is supply-driven and researcher initiated, applied research is demand-driven and challenge initiated. There are various platforms that have hosting applied research activities and innovations though with gaps that can be filled through establishing ARPE Centres.

Through ARPE centres it is possible to promote, coordinate and guide several innovations that are feted towards commercialization through pilot production and further industrial linkages. While some innovators in Kenya have been able to get breakthroughs in commercializing their innovations after rigorous processes seeking assistance, many young innovators especially still at training levels would suffer defeat on this without mentorship and guidance which can be easily availed if ARPE centres were established across technical institutes starting with 10 national polytechnics for pilot.

While some institutes have consciously or otherwise used applied research technologies to solve their own challenges, they have not yet addressed the gap between using such facilities for own training to input elements of scalability to allow the learners be able to do themselves at training levels. Coming up with a centre that can deliberately design such can help the institutions save on costs of operation as well as use their on infrastructure built on applied research as learning resources hence immensely contributing to quality of potential industrial labor and the innovative capacity of their earners.

Institutions can also add value to industrial visits and internships by first establishing a collaborative framework with the industries and coming up with structured targets for the visits and internship to add on the academic targets. Through a coordinating centre, such targets can help improve the centres when the students are engaged in ‘extra thinking’ to come up with alternative products and solutions based on their industrial observation. This can help domesticate the ideas gathered as well build a new knowledge repository for innovative learning as well industrial promotion.

Institutions can used applied research ideas to come up with pilot production units which can be industrially approved and serve as alternative income streams. This can be coupled with services that can be offered as consultancies on various thematic areas from amongst the trainers and other collaborators. This is the practical application of the knowledge to help bring solutions to challenges that can be first identified.

To achieve the above, institutions can strengthen relations with government departments and the private sector and improve ways of communication by establishing memorandum of understanding with other solution providers. All academic departments can centrally present their practical learning needs and through a central ARPE centre these proposals can be written and relayed through the MOUs and directly.

A correlation between an RPE and an ARPE has been made based on the structure of the JKUAT RPE and necessary adjustments can be made based on policy and feasibility issues. TVETA directorate of strategy research and planning can guide on the restructuring and decide if the ARPEs should be offered a new directorate in TVETA or shall be established based on the existing

divisions of research in national polytechnics. Nevertheless, what is overriding is the fact that the ARPE Centres need key functions handling: linkages; innovations; identifiable feasible thematic areas; proposal writing; school innovations and community outreach; production /income generating units and/or parks; research & consultancy.

Thematic areas should be led and linked to strategic industrial players with whose collaboration the idea of ARPEs can be entrenched. Starting with 10 national polytechnics in Kenya can pilot the idea which can later be replicated in other technical institutes. It is true indeed, that '*establishing TVET ARPE Centres in national polytechnics can spur industrialization*'.

Conflict of interest declaration

In the course of the research work up to the recommendations, this author declares that he did it out of a professional urge to bring up the idea for the good of all the target institutions and that there was no conflict of interest that guided the research.

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